

AgriBrain – AI Powered Farming with Intelligent Agriculture Advisor

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Abstract - This paper presents a AgriBrain – AI Powered Farming with Intelligent Agriculture Advisor designed to provide real-time support to farmers through text and voice interaction. The system offers crop management advice, weather forecasts, pest and disease identification, and market price updates using NLP and live data integration. Image recognition is incorporated for accurate crop disease diagnosis. By delivering region-specific and timely information, the proposed solution helps improve farm productivity and decision-making.

Keywords- *Artificial Intelligence, Smart Agriculture, Agricultural Chatbot, Gemini AI, Crop Disease Detection, Speech-to-Text, Image Processing, Real-Time Weather Monitoring, Market Price Prediction, Precision Farming.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Agriculture plays a vital role in the economies of developing nations but faces challenges such as unpredictable weather, pests, fluctuating market prices, and limited access to expert guidance. AgriBrain – AI Powered Farming with Intelligent Agriculture Advisor help bridge this gap by providing farmers with real-time, accessible support through text and voice in regional languages. These virtual assistants offer services such as crop management advice, weather forecasting, pest and disease identification, and market updates. Advanced NLP, image recognition, and live data integration enable accurate, region-specific recommendations. Government initiatives like PM-KISAN have further enhanced farmer outreach through such intelligent digital platforms. Real-time weather forecasts and alerts help farmers plan activities.

OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGY

Objectives

- To develop an interactive multilingual chatbot that assists farmers in their local language.
- To provide real-time weather forecasts, market crop prices, and agricultural news updates.
- To integrate fertilizer calculation and budget expense management for better farm planning.
- To ensure easy access and usability through a responsive web interface.
- To empower farmers with data-driven insights for improved decision-making and productivity.

Methodology

The project begins with identifying the challenges faced by farmers and analysing the requirements for multilingual support. The chatbot is designed using a modular architecture that integrates Speech-to-Text, Text to-Speech, and Translation APIs along with Gemini AI for generating smart farming responses. Image processing is used for crop disease detection, while external APIs provide weather and market data. A user-friendly mobile interface is developed using react and Nodejs to support voice, text, and image inputs. The overall methodology includes design, development, integration, testing, and deployment to ensure smooth performance across devices. In the design phase, the overall system architecture is prepared by dividing the system into frontend, backend, database, and external API layers. The frontend interface is designed using React to support voice, text, and image inputs.

Fig1:- flow chart of AgriBrain

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Recent studies show that AI-based chatbots in agriculture help farmers obtain quick crop-related guidance and improve decision-making. Several researchers have developed multilingual and voice-enabled agricultural chatbots to overcome literacy and language barriers in rural areas. Plant disease detection using image processing and deep learning has achieved high accuracy, but most models work as standalone systems. AI-driven decision support **systems** integrate weather and crop data to improve productivity and resource management. However, existing systems usually provide only one or two services such as chat, disease detection, or weather updates. There is a lack of a single unified platform integrating chatbot, voice support, image-based detection, real-time data, and financial tracking. The proposed AgriBrain system bridges this research gap by combining all these features into one smart agricultural advisory platform.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed solution is the development of AgriBrain – an AI-powered intelligent agriculture advisor that delivers smart, real-time farming support through a unified digital platform. The system integrates multiple advanced technologies to assist farmers in decision-making, crop management, and financial planning.

1. User Interface Design

A simple, user-friendly, and responsive web/mobile interface is designed using React to support easy navigation. The interface allows farmers to interact using voice, text, and image inputs, making it accessible even for users with limited digital literacy.

Fig2:- User Interface

2. AI Chatbot and Multilingual Support

The core of the system is an AI-powered chatbot using Gemini AI, which provides intelligent, crop-specific farming guidance. Speech-to-Text and

Translation APIs enable interaction in regional languages, improving usability for rural farmers.

Fig3:- Language Selection

3. Image-Based Crop Disease Detection

The system allows farmers to upload crop images, which are analysed using image processing techniques to detect possible diseases and provide basic preventive suggestions.

Fig4:- Image detection

4. Real-Time Weather and Market Information

AgriBrain integrates live Weather, Market Price, and News APIs to provide real-time updates that help farmers plan irrigation, harvesting, and crop selling effectively.

Fig5:- Weather Detection

Fig6:- Live Market Price

Agriculture News

Fig7:- Live news

5. Budget, Expense, and History Management

A digital budget and expense tracker helps farmers maintain financial records, while the history

module stores all previous interactions for future reference and analysis.

Fig8:- Budget&Expense Tracker

History

Fig9:- History

6. Backend Processing and Data Storage

The backend, developed using Node.js/Python, handles request processing, AI integration, API communication, and secure database storage (MongoDB/MySQL) of user data and activity logs.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

a. System Components

Component	Technology Used	Purpose
Frontend	React	User Interface
Backend	Node.js	Input Processing
AI Engine	Gemini AI	Smart Farming Responses
Speech Module	STT API	Voice Input
Image Module	Basic Image Processing	Crop Issue Detection
APIs	Weather, Market, News	Real-time Data
Database	MongoDB	Data Storage

b. Test Cases

Test ID	Test scenario	Input	Expected output	Status
TC_01	Text Query Processing	“How to Grow tomatoes?”	Chatbot provides tomato farming guidelines in selected language	Pass
TC_02	Language switching	User selects Telugu	Entire chatbot interface and responses switch to Telugu	Pass
TC_03	Weather API response	Location = "Hyderabad"	System fetches and displays weather forecast	Pass
TC_04	Market price retrieval	User query: "Tomato price?"	Current market rate displayed	Pass
TC_05	Image upload for disease detection	Uploaded leaf image	System identifies disease (if any) and suggests treatment	Pass
TC_06	Chat history retrieval	User opens previous chat	Past conversation displayed correctly	Pass
TC_07	Voice Input Recognition	User speaks: “Weather Today?”	Voice is converted to text and processed correctly	Pass

V. DISCUSSION

1. Usability and User Experience:

AgriBrain is designed with a simple, user-friendly, and intuitive interface so that farmers can easily interact with the system without technical difficulty. The support for voice, text, and image inputs makes the platform accessible even to users with low digital literacy. Multilingual interaction further improves usability by allowing farmers to communicate in their regional languages, enhancing comfort, trust, and adoption of the system.

2. Applications in Real-World Scenarios:

In real-world conditions, AgriBrain can be used by farmers for daily crop guidance, weather-based farming decisions, market price monitoring, and disease identification through images. It can support rural farming communities, Krishi Vigyan Kendras, FPOs, and government agricultural programs for digital advisory services. The expense tracking and history features also help farmers in

financial planning and record maintenance, improving overall farm management efficiency.

VI. CONCLUSION

The multilingual farmer chatbot provides farmers with instant access to essential information and smart tools for better decision-making, making farming more efficient and easier. The system helps farmers access live weather updates, live market prices, crop disease detection through images, voice-based communication, and multilingual responses, making agricultural guidance more accessible and personalized.

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